

Network Pharmacology-Based Investigation Of Asiatic Acid And Catharanthine Reveals Multi-Target Mechanisms Against Breast Cancer

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ABSTRACT

Network pharmacology has developed into a systems-based method that analyses the association between biologically active compounds and diverse biological targets. Unlike conventional single-target strategies, this method integrates computational tools to analyse complex drug-target relationships within biological networks, thereby supporting drug discovery and repositioning. One of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality among women worldwide is still breast cancer. The increasing drawbacks of conventional treatments, particularly their toxicity and adverse effects, have prompted the investigation of plant-derived compounds as potential therapeutic alternatives. In this regard, the present study employs a network pharmacology framework to evaluate the therapeutic potential of AA and Cath in BC. Potential targets of these chemicals were predicted using computer algorithms and publicly available data. We then filtered targets associated with breast cancer and generated compound-target and protein-protein interaction (PPI) networks. To better understand the molecular mechanisms, enrichment analyses were performed using the Kyoto Encyclopaedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) and Gene Ontology (GO). The results suggest that AA and Cath exert therapeutic effects through multi-target interactions and modulation of key biological pathways. Overall, this study establishes a systematic foundation for understanding the pharmacological mechanisms of these phytoconstituents in BC.

Keywords: Network pharmacology; breast cancer; molecular mechanism; GO analysis; KEGG analysis ; Protein-protein interaction.

INTRODUCTION

Network pharmacology has recently gained attention as a novel approach for investigating drug actions within complex biological systems. With traditional “one-drug-one-target” models, it primarily emphasizes multi-target interactions and network-based mechanisms, making it particularly relevant for multifactorial diseases such as cancer. By integrating bioinformatics, systems biology, and pharmacological data, this approach helps in the identification of potential therapeutic targets and pathways involved in disease progression. (1)

Breast cancer is among the most commonly diagnosed diseases worldwide and represents a leading cause of mortality among women. Its pathogenesis involves genetic and epigenetic alterations that disrupt normal cellular functions and activate key signalling

pathways responsible for tumor initiation and progression (2)

Global cancer data show that breast cancer has become the most diagnosed cancer globally, in 2020 it recorded 2.3million new cases. It is a highly heterogeneous disorder, at the molecular level. Key factors involved in its development include activation of HER2, hormone receptors such as oestrogen and progesterone receptors, and mutations in genes like BRCA. (3) Breast cancer is significantly impacting women’s health and contributing to high rates of illness and death. It is estimated that about one in eight women has chances to develop breast cancer. In the USA alone, nearly 297,790 new cases of invasive breast cancer have been reported, highlighting its high incidence. (4)

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The burden of breast cancer has increased significantly over recent years. With over 2.3 million new cases reported worldwide breast cancer has become the most frequently diagnosed cancer surpassing lung cancer, one in every eight cases. (5)

It is commonly managed using treatment modalities such as Drug-based treatment, operative procedures, radiological therapy, endocrine treatment, and precision-targeted therapies. Drug based approaches like Chemotherapy, in particular, is used after surgery or when surgery is not possible. However, these treatments are frequently associated with significant adverse effects, including fatigue, hair loss, nausea, early ovarian failure, increase in weight, and cardiac related issues, those can greatly impact a patient's quality of life. Despite progress in treatment, managing advanced and untreatable stages of cancer is still a major challenge, highlighting the need for safer and more therapeutic strategies. Medicinal plants in this context provides a valuable and sustainable bioactive compound source especially phytochemicals for cancer treatment. These natural compounds have shown potential in preventing early cancer development, reducing the aggressiveness of precancerous cells, and regulating important cellular procedures such as growth of cells and [Apoptosis](#). Nearly 3000 plant species and numerous bioactive compounds have been studied for their anticancer potential. (6)

The plant *Centella asiatica*, belonging to the Apiaceae family, has been utilised for centuries in traditional healthcare systems. It is widely recognised across Asian countries like China, India, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Malaysia, and Indonesia where it is known by various local names. (7) Asiatic acid, a pentacyclic triterpenoid derived from *Centella asiatica*, has been extensively investigated for its anticancer properties. (8)

Multiple reports stated that AA possesses a broad range of pharmacological properties. It has been shown to support wound healing, reduce inflammation, protect liver function, enhance neurocognitive performance, and help alleviate diabetic kidney damage. Recent findings further indicate its potential anticancer activity, as it has been shown to inhibit the proliferation of various cancer

cell lines, including those of liver, breast, tongue, prostate, melanoma, and nasopharyngeal origin. (9)

Belonging to Apocynaceae family *Catharanthus roseus* is a plant species and is widely recognized by the common name Madagascar periwinkle. Different plant parts of *Catharanthus roseus* contain a variety of bioactive compounds with medicinal significance. It has been used traditionally to manage several conditions, including cancer, and other ailments. The plant contains pharmacologically active secondary metabolites that have been isolated and utilised in the drug development for treating various diseases. *Catharanthus roseus* is particularly well known for its rich diversity of alkaloids. (10)

Due to the significant anticancer potential of vinca alkaloids, several semisynthetic derivatives have been developed, such as Vinorelbine and Vinflunine, which are structurally modified to enhance therapeutic effects. Following their discovery, both natural and synthetic forms of these alkaloids have been extensively evaluated in clinical studies to determine their effectiveness in breast cancer treatment. (11)

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Overview of Network Pharmacology

Network Pharmacology represents an interdisciplinary strategy that integrates systems biology, bioinformatics, and pharmacology to investigate the relationships among drugs, targets and diseases at a systemic level. Unlike the conventional "one-drug-one target" model, this emphasises multi-target and multi-pathway interactions, making it highly suitable for studying complex disorders such as cancer. (12,13)

This methodology facilitates the development of integrated biological networks, including compound-target associations, protein-protein interaction (PPI) networks, and pathway-based models, to better interpret pharmacological mechanisms. By combining computational prediction, target identification, and enrichment analysis, it enables the recognition of key molecular targets and signalling pathways involved in disease progression. (13,14)

Additionally, this strategy is particularly valuable for studying phytoconstituents, which often exert therapeutic effects through synergistic actions, thereby providing a scientific basis for understanding their therapeutic potential in diseases such as breast cancer. (15,16)

2.1.1. Selection of Compounds and Target Prediction

The bioactive compounds catharanthine and asiatic acid were selected for this study based on published scientific information. Relevant molecular data were taken from the PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) for further computer investigation, such as PubChem ID, molecular formula, molecular weight, canonical SMILES, and three-dimensional structures. (17, 18)

Potential protein targets of these compounds were predicted using computational Swiss Target Prediction (<https://www.swisstargetprediction.ch/>), which employs ligand-based similarity and pharmacophore-based modelling to identify probable biological targets. (18,19) This prediction strategy aligns with the multi-target network pharmacology, which is crucial for understanding complex disease mechanisms. (20,21).

2.1.2. Standardisation of Targets

The predicted targets were standardised using the UniProt database to ensure consistency in protein and gene nomenclature. Only human (*Homo sapiens*) targets with a probability score of ≥ 0.1 were retained, and duplicate entries were eliminated to enhance data accuracy and reliability. (17,22).

Breast cancer-related targets were obtained from the GeneCards (<https://www.genecards.org/>) database using the relevant keywords. These targets serve as an important resource for identifying key molecular pathways and potential therapeutic targets. (22). Due to its complex molecular mechanisms and involvement of multiple signalling pathways, breast cancer is well suited for network-based analysis. (18,23).

2.1.3. Identification of Common Targets

The predicted targets of AA and Catha were compared with breast cancer-associated targets to determine overlapping genes. The shared targets were visualised using VENNY 2.1.0 (<https://bioinfogp.cnb.csic.es/tools/ny/>) tool and were considered potential therapeutic candidates for further network pharmacology analysis. (17,19)

2.1.4. Construction of Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI) Network

The common targets were imported into the STRING (<https://string-db.org/>) database to construct a Protein-protein interaction (PPI) network, enabling the analysis of functional associations among proteins (20). Subsequently, KEGG pathway enrichment analysis was performed to identify significant signalling pathways related to the selected targets.

The resulting datasets, including genes, pathways, and targets were further processed using Cytoscape software (version 3.10.3) for network construction and integration. Topological parameters and nodes were ranked based on degree centrality to identify key targets. Nodes with higher connectivity were considered biologically important. Visual attributes such as node size and colour were adjusted according to degree values to enhance network interpretation.

2.1.5. GO and KEGG Enrichment Analysis

The STRING database was used to determine the functions of the identified targets using Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment analysis, including Biological Process (BP), Molecular Function (MF), and Cellular Component (CC) (18, 20). To determine their functional importance in breast cancer, the top GO keywords were analysed (19, 22). The significance cut-off was set at p -value < 0.05 . KEGG pathway enrichment analysis was also carried out to identify the primary pathways associated with the selected targets. To gain insight into their role during the disease process, pathways reaching the significance threshold (p -value < 0.05) were further explored (24)

3. RESULTS

3.1.1. Identification of Compound-Related Targets

A comprehensive set of potential targets associated with AA and Cath was obtained from the PubChem database. A total of 67 targets of Asiatic acid and 52 targets for Catharanthine were predicted using SwissTargetPrediction. After removing duplicate entries and standardising through the UniProt database, a refined list of targets was generated.

Breast cancer-related genes were retrieved from the Gene Cards database. The dataset included 18887 common targets, representing overlapping genes between selected compounds and breast cancer (Figure 1). These disease-associated targets provided a reference framework for identifying therapeutically relevant overlaps with compound-derived targets.

2. Identification of Compound-Target Network

The compound-target network was constructed using Cytoscape 3.10.3 to understand how Asiatic acid and Catharanthine interact with different protein targets. This network included 20 active compounds and 18887 associated targets.

The AA network consisted of 68 nodes and 281 edges, while the Catharanthine network included 51 nodes and 121 edges. In this representation, nodes correspond to compounds or targets, and edges indicate their interactions. Further analysis enabled the identification of key targets based on degree centrality.

Figure 1 Potential targets of Asiatic Acid and Catharanthine in Breast Cancer

A. Venn Diagram

B. Asiatic Acid -Disease Merged Network

C. Catharanthine -Disease Merged Network

.1.2. Protein-Protein Interaction Network of Targets

Figure 2 Protein-protein interaction (PPI) network and hub gene analysis

Asiatic Acid

The identified common targets were imported into the String database (Figure 2 (A) to analyse the interactions between proteins. KEGG pathway enrichment further revealed 21 significant pathways for Asiatic acid and 29 pathways for Catharanthine. Topological analysis highlighted several hub genes. For Asiatic acid IL6 showed the highest degree value (52), followed by PPARG (24), PPARA (24), HMGCR (22) and PTGS2 (20), indicating their central role in the network.

Rank	Node
1	IL6
2	PPARG
3	PPARA
4	HMGCR
5	PTGS2
6	ESR1
7	PTGS1
7	PPARD
9	NR3C1
10	NR1H4

Asiatic Acid

Rank	Node
1	CHRNA4
2	CHRNA4
3	ACHE
4	CHRNA3
5	CHRM2
6	DRD2
7	CHRM4
8	CHRM1
9	CHRNA7
10	SLC18A3

Catharanthine

Figure 2. PPI network and key targets. (A) PPI network, the higher value the degree of the node in the network, the larger the node and the darker the color, otherwise, vice versa. The higher value of the combined score of the connection between the nodes, the thicker the connection and darker the color. (B) Circular network presentation of the top 10 hub genes identified using the Cytohubba plugin in Cytoscape based on degree centrality. Nodes represent genes, and ranking is based on connectivity within the network. (C) Network Visualization showing hub genes identified based on degree values. Node size and color intensity represent the degree of connectivity.

In case of Catharanthine, key targets included CHR4, CHRNB4, ACHE, CHR4 and CHR2 were among the top-ranked nodes, followed by DRD2, CHR4, CHR1, CHR4 and SLC18A3. These targets are primarily associated with neurotransmitter signalling and receptor activity, suggesting a distinct but complementary mechanism of action compared to AA.

results indicated significant involvement in inflammatory response, lipid metabolism and regulation of cell proliferation. Molecular function analysis showed enrichment in receptor activity and enzyme binding, whereas cellular component analysis suggested localised predominantly within the plasma membrane cytoplasm and nucleus. These findings indicate the involvement of targets in signalling pathways, intracellular processes and gene regulation relevant to breast cancer.

3.1.3. GO Enrichment Analysis of Targets

Gene Ontology (GO) analysis was performed to understand the functions of the identified targets. The

Figure 3 Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment analysis

Asiatic Acid Biological Process

B. Catharanthine Biological Process

C. Asiatic Acid Molecular Function

D. Catharanthine Molecular Function

E. Asiatic Acid Cellular Component

F. Catharanthine Cellular Component

Figure 3. GO Enrichment Analysis of Targets. (A) GO enrichment analysis of Asiatic Acid Biological process. (B) GO enrichment analysis of Catharanthine Biological process. (C) GO enrichment analysis of Asiatic Acid Molecular Function. (D) GO enrichment analysis of Catharanthine Molecular Function. (E) GO Enrichment Analysis of Asiatic acid Cellular Component. (F) GO Enrichment Analysis of Catharanthine Cellular Component

Gene Ontology analysis showed that the predicted targets of Asiatic acid were mostly associated with functions such as nuclear receptor activity (GO:0004879), steroid binding (GO:0005496), eicosanoid receptor activity (GO:0004953), monocarboxylic acid binding (GO:00033293) and prostaglandin receptor activity (GO:0004955). The greatest number of genes enriched and the strongest statistical significance were found for nuclear receptor activity and steroid binding activity. This suggests that these functions may be the main mode of action of Asiatic acid.

The enriched molecular functions for catharanthine were acetylcholine receptor activity (GO:0015464), neurotransmitter receptor activity (GO:0030594), postsynaptic neurotransmitter receptor activity (GO:0098960), G protein-coupled acetylcholine receptor activity (GO:0016907) and G protein-coupled serotonin receptor activity (GO:0004993). In particular, neurotransmitter receptor activity and acetylcholine receptor activity were associated with the most genes and highly significant. This indicates that these receptor-related functions are likely central to the mechanism of action of Catha.

3.1.4. KEGG Enrichment Analysis of Targets

KEGG pathway analysis revealed multiple significantly enriched pathways associated with both compounds.

Figure 4 KEGG pathway enrichment analysis

For Asiatic acid, the major pathways included:

- PPAR signalling pathway
- Arachidonic acid metabolism
- Ovarian steroidogenesis
- Insulin resistance
- Pathways in cancer
- Steroid hormone biosynthesis

These pathways are closely related to cancer progression, metabolic regulation and hormone signalling.

Catharanthine KEGG Pathways

Figure 4. KEGG Pathways enrichment. (A) Bubble plot representing the top enriched KEGG pathways of Asiatic acid. The size of the nodes indicates gene count and color represents statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). (B) Bubble plot representing the top enriched KEGG pathways of Catharanthine. The size of the nodes indicates gene count and color represents statistical significance ($p < 0.05$).

For Catharanthine, the major pathways included:

- Neuroactive ligand-receptor interaction
- Cholinergic synapse
- cAMP signalling pathway
- Hepatitis B
- Regulation of actin cytoskeleton

These pathways are closely related to cancer progression.

The KEGG enrichment results were visualised using a bubble plot, in which pathways were ranked according to statistical significance ($p < 0.05$), while gene count was represented by colour gradient and node size, respectively.

Overall, the findings suggest that Asiatic acid primarily regulates metabolic and cancer-related pathways, whereas Catharanthine predominantly targets neurotransmitter-related receptors and signalling mechanisms. Collectively, these phytoconstituents demonstrate a multi-target and multi-pathway mechanism, indicating their potential in breast cancer treatment.

4. DISCUSSION

The present study applied a network pharmacology approach to explore the therapeutic potential of Asiatic acid and Catharanthine in breast cancer. The findings indicate that both compounds act through a multi-target mechanism, which is consistent with the complex nature of cancer. (20,21). This finding aligns with the concept of network pharmacology as a system-level strategy in modern drug discovery (25).

Analysis of the protein-protein interaction network helps identify hub genes with high degree centrality, suggesting their key regulatory role in disease progression. Such hub proteins are known to influence multiple signalling cascades and are often considered critical targets in cancer research. (17,22,26).

Functional enrichment further indicated that the identified targets participate in critical biological processes such as cell proliferation, apoptosis and oxidative stress response. These processes are fundamental to tumour development and progression, highlighting the relevance of the predicted targets. Comparable findings have been reported in earlier studies examining the role of phytoconstituents in cancer-associated pathways. (19,22,27).

Pathway enrichment analysis offered further insight into the molecular mechanisms associated with the selected compounds. Asiatic acid was primarily

associated with pathways such as PPAR signalling pathway, arachidonic acid metabolism, ovarian steroidogenesis, insulin resistance, pathways in cancer and steroid hormone biosynthesis. In contrast, Catharanthine showed enrichment in pathways such as Neuroactive ligand- receptor interaction, Cholinergic synapse, cAMP signalling pathway, Hepatitis B and Regulation of actin cytoskeleton.

Previous studies have reported that Asiatic acid has been exhibited anticancer effects through mechanisms such as inducing apoptosis and suppressing tumour cell proliferation. (13,28). Similarly, Catharanthine, derived from *Catharanthus roseus*, belongs to the vinca alkaloid class, which is well known for its anticancer properties and has been widely used in chemotherapy. (19,29). These findings support the results of the current study.

Overall, the findings indicate that Asiatic acid and Catharanthine act through multi-targets and multi-pathways, supporting their potential as therapeutic candidates for breast cancer. However, further validation through molecular docking and experimental studies is required to confirm these findings. (30)

In conclusion, this study indicates that Asiatic acid and catharanthine exhibit therapeutic potential against breast cancer through multi-target and multi-pathway mechanisms. Key signalling pathways, including PI3K-Akt, MAPK, and apoptosis-related pathways, were significantly influenced. These results highlight the promise of these phytoconstituents as promising candidates for breast cancer therapy. However, further validation through molecular docking and experimental studies is required to confirm these mechanisms and establish their clinical relevance.

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6.CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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